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The cost of CCS – a product chain analysis of the cement and pulp industries

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Abstract

Global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions need to be net-zero around mid-century and net-negative thereafter to comply with the Paris Agreement and restrict global warming to less than 2°C with reasonable certainty. Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) can be implemented to mitigate fossil-based emissions from the cement industry and to create negative emissions in the sulfate pulp industry. However, the application of CCS on basic material production typically results in large increases in production costs due to investment costs of the capture plant and increased operational cost to power the capture process. This work quantifies the change in costs and CO₂-emissions in a product chain perspective when introducing CCS in cement and Kraft pulp production. The changes are explored through end-product case studies for the cement and pulp industries for a high-speed railway and disposable baby diaper, respectively. The results show that the production cost of cement increases by 230-260% when applying CCS with 90% capture rate and a carbon price of 80€/tCO₂ on non-abated fossil emissions. However, the production cost for the end-product, the high-speed railway, only increases by 1.4-2.0%. Similarly, the production cost of pulp increases by 75-130% when applying CCS on two out of three emissions sources at the Kraft pulp mill with an overall capture rate of 77.5%, but the production cost of the end-product, the disposable baby diaper, only increases by 3.3-4.8%.

Keywords: product chain; value chain; CCS; Bio-CCS; cement; pulp; negative emissions; carbon footprint

1. Introduction

Global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions need to be net-zero around mid-century and net-negative thereafter to comply with the Paris Agreement and restrict global warming to less than 2°C with reasonable certainty. Industry accounted for approximately 20% of global GHG emissions in 2019. The cement industry accounts for 6-7% of global fossil-fuel based GHG emissions and the process related emissions (from the calcination process) can only be mitigated by means of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS). Negative emissions are required to compensate for residual emissions in hard-to-abate sectors such as agriculture and aviation and to compensate for a likely overshoot in emissions, i.e. net negative emissions are likely to be required in the second half of the century. Negative emissions can be generated by applying CCS on existing large point sources of biogenic carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions provided that the biomass feedstock is sourced from a system for which the carbon stock is at least maintained or with a net growth (e.g., by means of a well-developed forest management system). Such emission sources can be sulfate pulp mills for which the global capture potential on existing mills has been estimated to 135 Mtonne CO₂ per year [1]. However, applying CCS to basic material production, including cement and the pulp and paper industry, is known to result in large increases in production costs due to the high investment and operational costs of CCS. Yet, previous

work has shown that even if the production costs increases significantly when CCS is implemented, the cost of the end-products in the value chains of these materials increase only marginally (see e.g., [2] and [3]).

Costs of implementing CCS in industrial plants differ significantly depending on factors such as emission volumes and CO₂ concentration in the flue gas, availability of excess heat to drive part of the capture process, logistical conditions for transport to CO₂ storage sites, and whether CCS is implemented as part of a new-built plant or retrofitted to an existing plant. Furthermore, the extent to which an increase in production costs of basic materials can be passed on through the product chains to the end-consumer also differs between materials and products. It is therefore interesting to follow-up on previous studies with more case studies representing various of the above-mentioned conditions. In this study, we further investigate the effects on costs and carbon footprints along the product chain from basic material to end-product for the case of post-combustion CCS applied to a cement plant and a market Kraft pulp mill to abate fossil and process related emissions and to generate negative emissions, respectively. The analysis is carried out as two product chain case studies: cement to a high-speed railway that is about considered to be built in Sweden, and pulp to a disposable baby diaper as end-product. Thus, including two highly different types of end-products.

The study is general in that it investigates the cost along the product chain for CCS mitigation efforts and does not include any spatial or time information (other than that it assumes condition relevant for the EU-27). The overall aim with the work is to illustrate the impact on cost and emissions on the end-product from CCS as a deep mitigation measure.

Nomenclature

adt	Air dried tonne
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CEPCI	Chemical engineering plant cost index
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CO _{2,eq}	Carbon dioxide equivalents
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
RMC	Ready-mix concrete
TCR	Total Capital Requirement
TIC	Total Plant Installed Cost
TPC	Total Plant Cost

2. Methodology

This paper is based on the concept of product chain analysis and aims to provide estimates of changes in costs and emissions through the product chain of specific end-products due to the installation of CCS in the cement and Kraft pulp industry. Firstly, the product chain from raw material extraction to end-product is mapped out, and the production cost of the basic material is calculated to see how the change in production cost and selling price, including profit margins, affects the cost of the end-product. Finally, since the aim of applying CCS to the basic material production is climate change mitigation, the change in emissions in the initial and final step of the product chain is calculated.

2.1. Product chain analysis: From raw material extraction to end-product

The product chains studied in this work starts with the extraction of raw material (limestone in the cement case and biomass for the pulp case), continues with the production of the basic material (cement or pulp), and production of intermediate product (concrete), and the material is then to be used in an end-product (cement and concrete in the high-speed railway and fluff pulp in the disposable baby diaper). Figure 1 shows an overview of the product chain and the system boundaries considered for the economic evaluation (represented in yellow) and emission calculations

(represented in green). Transportation occurs in between each main activity in the product chain and fuels and/or electricity as well as other materials are used or added along the chain. The present work does not consider a full Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) with respect to emissions. The reason is to illustrate the direct emission reduction of CCS and its associated cost on the product chain. A complete LCA would require assumptions on how emissions for energy supply and end-of-life of product changes over time and is considered outside the scope of this work. Therefore, the system boundary for the emission calculations differs from the cost evaluation as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of system boundaries for the economic evaluation (represented in yellow) and emission calculations (represented in green).

2.1. Basic material

The configuration of the cement plant, including integration of CCS, is based on the work by IEAGHG [4], [5]. The cement plant has an assumed production capacity of 1.5 Mtonne cement per year. During the calcination process in the lime kiln, both process-based and fuel-based emissions are created. The process-based emissions account for approximately two thirds out of the total emissions and occur due to the decomposition of carbonate material originating from the input raw material, limestone. The fuel mixed used in the cement kiln/precalciner for the base case is taken from Rootzén et al. [6] and it is assumed that 3025 MJ/t_{cement} of thermal energy is required in the cement kiln/precalciner [2].

The configuration of the Kraft pulp mill, including integration of CCS, is based on the work by Onarheim [8], [9]. The Kraft pulp mill has three main point emission sources: the recovery boiler, the lime kiln and the multi-fuel boiler (also referred to as power boiler or bark boiler). The pulp mill has an assumed production capacity of 0.8 Madt pulp per year with the raw material being assumed to be pine and spruce (50%/50%). More than simply producing pulp, the mill is co-producing crude tall oil and electricity, both of which are sold on the market thereby generating an income to the mill. The biomass used in the mill is assumed to have been sustainably produced, meaning that the electricity and heat produced is considered renewable. The total fuel consumption in the recovery boiler, lime kiln and multi-fuel boiler is assumed to 42.4 GJ/adt_{pulp} [8].

In this work, a conventional post-combustion amine-based CO₂ capture process is assumed with a 90% capture rate. To run the CCS plant in the cement case, an additional power plant is needed to be installed to generate steam for the regeneration of the absorbent. The power plant is assumed to be a natural gas combined cycle and the additional energy needed for capturing CO₂ is assumed to 2.8 GJ/tCO₂ captured [4]. For the Kraft pulp mill, CCS is applied to two out of three emissions sources, the recovery boiler and the lime kiln, resulting in an overall capture rate of 77.5%. The economic lifetime of the CCS plant is assumed to 25 years with a discount rate of 8% [4], [8]. Furthermore, a transportation and storage cost of CO₂ has been given in the range 35-50 €/tCO₂ in literature [10], [11], and an average value of 42.5 €/tCO₂ is used in this work. However, a sensitivity analysis of the parameter is made varying it between -50% to +100%.

Table 1 provides a summary of the general assumptions for the cement plant and pulp mill.

Table 1. General assumptions for the basic material production plants (cement plant and pulp mill).

General assumptions	Cement plant	Kraft pulp mill
Production capacity	1.5 Mt cement per year	0.8 Madt pulp per year
Average capacity utilisation rate ^a	91.3%	95.9%
Discount rate	8%	8%
Economic lifetime	25 years	25 years
Average transportation costs		
Delivery cost ^b	15€ per tonne of cement	15€ per tonne of adt pulp
Average market price per unit	64€ ₂₀₂₀ per tonne of cement ^c	1099€ ₂₀₂₁ per tonne of air-dried market pulp ^d

^a Roussanaly et al., 2021.

^b IEAGHG, 2013.

^c European Commission, 2018. Recalculated to €₂₀₂₀ using cement price index [14].

^d Average market price on the European market per tonne of bleached softwood market pulp [15].

End-product

The high-speed railway studied is a major infrastructure project being built Sweden. A significant part of the railway is planned to be ballast-less track, meaning that large amounts of cement and concrete is used to replace the railway sleepers and ballast used in conventional railways. The main materials used in the high-speed railway is concrete (>83wt%), steel products of varying type (rail, construction steel and reinforcement steel totaling in >5wt%), asphalt (4wt%), cement (3wt%) and additional limestone (2wt%). The concrete used in the construction is assumed to be ready-mix concrete (RMC) with a cement content of 18wt%. The railway will lead to production related emissions of approximately 7 Mtonne of carbon dioxide equivalents (CO_{2,eq}), depending on what mitigation options are available at the time of construction. Material use in the end-product will account for 75-80% of the LCA production related emissions, and cementitious materials alone makes up 45% of the total emissions from the project [16].

The material composition of the disposable baby diaper is taken from Mendoza et al. [17]. For the disposable paper diaper product, fluff pulp is a major constituent, contributing to approximately 32% of the mass composition of the finished end-product. Disposable diapers are a significant waste-stream currently accounting for 2.7% of the total municipal solid waste in the EU-28.

2.2. Cases

In this paper, five and four cases are considered for the cement and pulp product chain, respectively. A reference case represents a typical basic material plant in Year 2020 for both product chains. As mentioned above, a CCS case using post-combustion technology is applied for both material productions. For the cement product chain, a third case is considered where a CO₂-tax is introduced on fossil-based emissions for the reference case (i.e., the “Reference case incl. CO₂-tax”), but no such case is explored for the pulp product chain since all emissions from the Kraft pulp mill is considered biogenic. Moreover, to represent the drastic cost increases in natural gas and electricity prices in 2022 due to the current geo-political situation also high-cost scenarios for the reference and CCS cases are explored (“Reference high cost case” and “CCS high cost case”) using average prices for natural gas and electricity in EU-27 from the first quarter of 2022. Table 2 provides an overview of the cases covered and its cost components for the basic material production. To determine the cost of the intermediate and end-product, additional OPEX and overhead costs are added. For the intermediate product, a profit margin is also added to determine the selling price of each material.

Table 2: Overview of cases included in this study and their respective cost components in the basic material production. Included cost components for respective case is marked in grey.

	Cement	Pulp	Cement		Cement	Pulp
	Ref case	Ref high cost case	Ref case incl. CO ₂ tax	Ref high cost case incl. CO ₂ tax	CCS case	CCS high cost case
Basic material production	Production cost		Production cost		Production cost	
	CAPEX		CAPEX		CAPEX	
	OPEX	OPEX high	OPEX	OPEX high	OPEX	OPEX high
	Delivery cost		Delivery cost		Delivery cost	
	CO ₂ -tax		CO ₂ -tax		CO ₂ -tax	
	Transport and storage		Transport and storage		Transport and storage	
	Selling price		Selling price		Selling price	
	Profit margin		Profit margin		Profit margin	

2.3. Costs

In the following section, the methodology for the cost evaluation is described. Since this work considers a retrofit of two existing basic material production facilities (a cement plant and a Kraft pulp mill) with CCS, the CAPEX of the basic material plant itself has been depreciated. The basic material plants are assumed to be located in Europe and the CCS plant is Nth of a kind. The CAPEX for the CCS plant is expressed as annualized Total Capital Requirement (TCR) which includes direct costs for components, costs for retrofitting the mill, contingency costs, spare part cost (1% of TPC), start-up cost (3% of TPC), owner’s cost^a (7% of TPC), working capital, and interest during the construction phase (8%), see Figure 2 for overview. The TCR for cement plant is obtained from the work by IEAGHG [4], and the Kraft pulp mill is taken from Onarheim et al. [8]. Both these works assume CO₂ transportation via pipeline, but in this work, it is assumed that the CO₂ is transported via shipping at a pressure of 7 bar which is commonly used

^a Covering the costs for example feasibility studies, improving infrastructure beyond the site boundary, and permitting and legal fees. For more detailed information, see [8].

in literature [18], [19] and at a temperature of -49.1°C [20]. The cost for conditioning and compression of CO_2 is taken from Deng et al., 2019 [20].

Figure 2: Break-down of TCR cost structure, adapted from Deng et al., 2019.

All costs and prices are adjusted using the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index (CEPCI) and expressed in €_{2020} . Historically, sectors that are deemed to be at risk of carbon leakage due to international cost competitiveness, including cement and pulp industry^b [21], have received free allocation of emissions allowances from the EU-ETS cap and trade system. According to Phase 4 of the system (2021-2030), these sectors will continue to receive 100% free allocation of emission allowances in the first half of the period [22]. However, the free allocation to the industrial sectors is planned to be phased out gradually from 2026 by 10% each year due to the implementation of the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), which will replace the free allocation as a means to reduce carbon leakage [23]. Here, a tax on fossil-based emissions of $80\text{€}/\text{tCO}_2$ is applied to compare the effect of a CO_2 cost similar to the EU-ETS allowance price in Year 2022 for the different cases.

The cost of product, $C_{s,p}^{\text{prod}}$ ($\text{€}/\text{t}_{\text{product}}$), with and without CCS for each product p (basic material, intermediate product or end-product), for each sector s , is evaluated according to Equation 1.

$$C_{s,p}^{\text{prod}} = \text{OPEX}_{s,p}^{\text{var}} + \text{OPEX}_{s,p}^{\text{fix}} + \text{CAPEX}_{s,p} + C_{s,p}^{\text{delivery}} + C^{\text{transport}} + C^{\text{tax}} \quad (1),$$

where $\text{OPEX}_{s,p}^{\text{var}}$ is the variable operational expenditures, $\text{OPEX}_{s,p}^{\text{fix}}$ is the fixed operational expenditures, $\text{TCR}_{s,p}$ is the annualized investment cost, $C_{s,p}^{\text{delivery}}$ is the delivery cost of the industrial product, $C^{\text{transport}}$ is the transportation and storage cost of CO_2 , and C^{tax} is the carbon tax.

$\text{CAPEX}_{s,p}$ is calculated according to Equation 2,

$$\text{CAPEX}_{s,p} = \frac{\text{TCR}_{s,p} \cdot i}{1 - (1+i)^{-L}} \quad (2),$$

where TCR is the Total Capital Requirement, i is the discount rate assumed to 8%, and L is the economic lifetime assumed to 25 years. The TCR of the CCS plant is scaled to the production capacity of the plants used in this work (see Table 1 and 2 according to Equation 3 [24]).

$$\text{TCR}_j = \text{TCR}_{\text{ref}} \cdot \left(\frac{P_j}{P_{\text{ref}}} \right)^n \quad (3),$$

where TCR_j is the TCR of the scaled emission source, TCR_{ref} is the TCR of the reference emissions source, P_j is the production capacity of the emission source to which the cost is scaled to, P_{ref} is the production capacity of the reference emissions source, and n being an equipment specific scaling factor, in this study set to 0.6 [24].

^b No CO_2 -emission allowances are purchased by the pulp mill due to the plant being a biogenic emissions source.

The fixed OPEX includes costs for labor, maintenance, and other fixed costs. The cost for direct labor for industry in EU-27 is assumed to 60k€/year per person [25] and with an indirect labor cost of 40% the direct labor cost [7]. It is further assumed that 95 [5] and 120 [8] personnel are needed to run the cement plant and Kraft pulp mill, respectively, and that an increased capacity of 20 personnel per year is needed to run the CCS plant. The variable OPEX includes costs for raw materials, chemicals, fuel, other utilities, waste disposal and cost for electricity. Average electricity prices of 81.9 €/MWh for year 2020 and of 201 €/MWh for the high-cost scenario [26] are assumed and a selling price for crude tall oil of 500 €/ton. Energy is needed to run the CCS plant compared to the reference case meaning that more energy is used internally for the regeneration of the sorbent, and less electricity is sold to the grid in the pulp CCS case. However, for the Kraft pulp mill, the same amount of crude tall oil is produced in the cases with and without CCS. See Table 3 for an overview of the total costs for the reference case and CCS case respectively.

The selling price of the basic material for the reference case is determined by market prices for cement and pulp on the European market [13], [15]. The selling price of material for the CCS cases are then determined by the difference in cost compared to the reference case.

Table 3: Overview of costs for the reference case and CCS case respectively per tonne of product for cement or pulp. The high-cost scenario is presented in parenthesis.

Costs	Cement plant			Kraft pulp mill			
	Case	Ref case (high cost)	Ref case incl. CO ₂ -tax (high cost)	CCS case (high cost)	Ref case (high cost)	CCS case (high cost)	
CAPEX	-	-	19	€/t cement	-	51	€/adt pulp
Fixed OPEX	17	17	33	€/t cement	82	98	€/adt pulp
Variable OPEX	19 (29)	19 (29)	62 (113)	€/t cement	343 (377)	372 (487)	€/adt pulp
CO ₂ -tax	-	80	80	€/tCO ₂	-	-	€/tCO ₂
Transport and storage cost of CO ₂	-	-	43	€/tCO ₂	-	43	€/tCO ₂
CO ₂ capture cost ^a	-	-	99 (162)	€/tCO ₂	-	73 (97)	€/tCO ₂
Income							
Electricity exported to the grid	-	-	-	€/t cement	92 (227)	40 (99)	€/adt pulp
Crude tall oil sales	-	-	-	€/t cement	20	20	€/adt pulp

^a The CO₂ capture cost is calculated as the sum of the annualized CCS plant cost, additional variable and fixed OPEX compared to the base case. Costs for transportation and storage of CO₂ is excluded.

2.4. Emissions

Table 4 presents the specific emissions and the amount of captured CO₂ per tonne of product produced for each sector and case. Biomass used in production is assumed to be sustainably produced with respect to maintaining the carbon stock in the biomass system (e.g., the forests supplying the biomass), meaning that biogenic emissions are assumed to account as zero emissions in this work. The cement plant has both fossil-based and biogenic emissions while the Kraft pulp mill only has biogenic emissions. This means that the specific emissions for the Kraft pulp mill base case is equal to zero. Furthermore, all negative emissions created by applying CCS to the Kraft pulp mill are allocated to the pulp production and none to the co-produced products (crude tall oil and electricity sold to the grid).

As indicated previously, the emissions associated with the raw material extraction and the transportation step to basic material production plant has not been included for the calculation of the specific emissions for basic material production (*cf.* Figure 1). Moreover, for the CCS case, the emissions associated with transporting and storing the CO₂ after capturing has not been included. This means that the results for CO₂ emission reductions on the end-product represents the maximum reduction that can be achieved, since including emissions or leakage downstream the capture might somewhat reduce the emission reduction.

The emission calculation of the end-product is based on two already-made LCAs. The LCA of the high-speed railway is made by the Swedish Transport Administration and the LCA of the disposable baby diaper is based on work by Mendoza et al. [17].

Table 4: Overview of specific emissions and captured CO₂ per sector and case.

Emissions	Cement plant			Kraft pulp mill		
	Base case	Base case w. CO ₂ -tax	CCS case	Base case	CCS case	
Specific emissions ^a	0.7	0.7	0.07	0	-2.11	tCO ₂ /adt pulp
Captured CO ₂	-	-	0.6	-	2.11	tCO ₂ /adt pulp

^a Assuming production of biomass maintains carbon stock in biomass system (and biogenic emissions therefore accounting as climate neutral).

2.5. Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis is made of three input cost variables: the CO₂ capture cost, the CO₂ transportation and storage cost, and the delivery cost of the basic material. All parameters are varied from -50% to +100% compared to the original input value to test the sensitivity to cost variations. An additional sensitivity analysis is made of how the TCR and variable OPEX impact the CO₂ capture cost. The parameters are varied $\pm 20\%$.

3. Results

In the following section, the results for the differences in costs and emissions through the product chain for the different cases are presented as well as a sensitivity analysis of input parameters on the results.

3.1. Costs

Figure 3 shows the relative cost increase compared to the reference case through the product chain from basic material to end-product for the cement industry (see Figure 3a and high-cost case in Figure 3b). The basic material production cost increases significantly, 227% and 261% for the high-cost scenario, when applying CCS. However, when moving further down the product chain the relative cost increase reduces and for the end-product the increase is merely 1.4 and 2.0% for the high-cost scenario for the cement case study. Similar occur for the reference case including CO₂-tax. The cement production cost increases by 91 and by 108% for the high-cost scenario, while the end-product cost increases by 0.68% for both scenarios.

Figure 3: Cost impacts along the product chain of cement (Figure 3a) and high-cost scenario (Figure 3b) expressed in relative cost increase compared to the reference case or reference case for the high-cost scenario. The production cost for the reference case is set as reference (51.5€/t_{cement} or 61.1€/t_{cement} for the high-cost case). The numbers on the horizontal axis (1-7 for the cement case study) indicate the step of the product chain for which the cost is evaluated.

Similarly, Figure 4 show the relative cost impact along the product chain for the pulp industry, with Figure 4b being the high-cost scenario. The pulp production cost increases by 75-131% when applying CCS while the cost of the end-product just increases by 3.3-4.8%.

a. b. Figure 4: Cost impacts along the product chain of pulp (Figure 4a) and the high-cost scenario (Figure 4b) expressed in relative cost increase compared to the reference case or high-cost reference case. The production cost for the base case is set as reference (328€/adt_{pulp} or 270€/adt_{pulp}). The numbers on the horizontal axis (1-4 for the pulp case study) indicate the step of the product chain for which the cost is evaluated.

Figure 5 shows the production cost for cement (Figure 5a) and for pulp (Figure 5b) for the different cases. The total production cost of cement in the reference case is 51.5€ and 61.1€ per tonne of cement for the high-cost scenario. When a CO₂-tax of 80€/tCO₂ is introduced on fossil-based emissions, the production cost of cement changes significantly to more than double, to 107€ or 117€ per tonne of cement for the high-cost scenario. For the CCS case the production cost is further increased to 167€/t cement and 220€/t cement for the high-cost scenario due to additional operational expenditures, the capital cost of the CCS plant, and the transport and storage cost of CO₂. Moreover, if a CO₂-tax of 168€/tCO₂ would be introduced, the production cost of cement for the Reference case incl. CO₂-tax would be equal to the production cost for the CCS case.

The total production cost of pulp for the reference case and CCS case is 328 and 270€/adt pulp respectively, out of which the operational expenditures make out the largest share. The pulp production cost is evidentially smaller for the high-cost scenario due to the large revenues obtained from selling electricity at a high price to the grid. When adding CCS to the pulp production the total production cost increases due to capital cost of the CCS plant, the CO₂ transportation and storage cost as well as due to the decreased income of electricity sold to the grid.

Figure 5: Basic material production cost (cement in Figure 5a and pulp in Figure 5b) shown by cost parameter. Please note the different scales on the y-axis.

3.2. CO₂ emissions

Figures 6a and b show the CO₂-emissions reductions for the basic material and end-product for the cement case study and the pulp case study, respectively. As previously mentioned, the reductions in CO₂-emissions represent the maximum reduction potential due to the system boundary used for the calculations. The direct CO₂-emissions are reduced by approximately 90% for the cement and 77.5% for the pulp, respectively, and the LCA emissions for the end-product are reduced by 30% and 32% for the high-speed railway and the disposable baby diaper, respectively.

Figure 6: CO₂-emissions reductions experienced in the basic material production (cement product chain in Figure 6a and pulp product chain in Figure 6b) and end-product (high-speed railway or disposable baby diaper).

3.3. Sensitivity analysis

Figures 7 and 8 show the results from the sensitivity analysis of the capture cost, delivery cost and CO₂ transportation and storage cost for the cement and pulp product chains, respectively, with Figures 7a and 8a showing the impact on the basic material production, and Figures 7b and 8b on respective end-product. All parameters were varied from -50% to +100% compared to the original input value. The results for the relative cost increase compared to the reference case change rather significantly for the cement production cost, ranging from 148-386% cost increase (Figure 7a), with the largest impact originating from the change in CO₂ capture cost. However, when moving down the product chain to the results of the end-product production cost the range is 0.94-2.5% (Figure 7b), meaning that, as expected, even though the cost of cement would increase significantly due to larger than expected CO₂ capture costs, the cost of the end-product would not.

Figure 8 shows the corresponding results for the pulp product chain for the pulp production cost (Figure 8a) and end-product cost (Figure 8b). Like the cement case, the largest change in cost of pulp occur for the capture cost with a range of 50-122%, but this results in a small change of 2.2-5.3% for the end-product.

Figure 7: Sensitivity analysis for the production cost of cement (Figure 7a) and production cost of the high-speed railway (Figure 7b) of three parameters; cost for transportation and storage of CO₂, delivery cost, and capture cost of CO₂. Please note the different scales on the y-axis.

Figure 8: Sensitivity analysis for the production cost of pulp (Figure 8a) and production cost of the diaper (Figure 8b) of three parameters; cost for transportation and storage of CO₂, delivery cost, and capture cost of CO₂. Please note the different scales on the y-axis.

Figure 9 shows the results for the sensitivity analysis of CO₂ capture cost by TCR and variable OPEX for the cement industry (Figure 9a) and pulp industry (Figure 9b). As can be seen, the variable OPEX has a greater impact on the capture cost than the TCR for both industries.

Figure 9: Sensitivity analysis on how the TCR and variable OPEX affects the CO₂ capture cost excluding cost for transportation and storage for the cement industry (Figure 9a) and the pulp industry (Figure 9b).

4. Discussion

The results of the present work show that the CO₂-emissions related to each end-product could be decreased by roughly 30% when applying CCS in the basic material production. Simultaneously, the total production cost of the end-product is increased by only 1-5%. This is largely due to that the end-product related emissions mostly originate from the material production while most of the costs originate from construction and labour, meaning that the cost increase of basic material production will not have a great impact on the end-product production cost. The end-products emissions can therefore be reduced significantly to a marginal cost increase. Moreover, an important observation from the high-cost scenario and the sensitivity analysis is that even if the costs increase significantly in the initial step of the product chain, the relative cost increase of the end-product will remain low.

In this work, full cost pass-through is assumed, meaning that cost increases in the basic material production is fully passed on down-stream the product chain to the end-consumer. This is to illustrate how such a cost increase could possibly affect the consumer. However, actors along the product chain could internalize some of the additional costs, making the cost increase on the end-product even smaller. Policy models such as state guarantees through reversed auctioning could be used to incentivize and create markets for negative emissions [27]. Such a policy model can be motivated by the fact that producing negative emissions gives a cost for the emitter who mitigates the biogenic emissions but where the benefits are shared by all. Yet, it is reasonable to assume that in the longer run there should be a market developed for negative emissions involving sectors with emissions which are hard to abate. There is also a need for EU to introduce some type of CO₂ removal credits [28] if to comply with the proposed targets on climate neutrality by 2050 [29].

Providing a product with low climate impact, such as cement, or a product with negative emissions, such as pulp, can be viewed as additional value added to the product itself. This could lead to an increased willingness to pay for consumers, meaning that the product could be sold at an increased (premium) price compared to the original product, suggesting a larger revenue for the producer. The two products investigated here are obviously very different when it comes to their type of customer. In the cement product chain chosen, the final customer of the high-speed railway is typically a state-owned organization (in the Swedish case, the National Transport Administration) whereas the selected pulp product chain, has private consumers as customers. The former customer has clearly defined targets agreeing with the Swedish Governmental climate targets (net zero emissions by Year 2045) whereas the latter depends on the willingness to pay among private consumers for climate positive products (albeit the results from this study shows that cost would only need to be marginally increased). In both cases the main issue is what information is required for

the basic material producer to invest in CCS, i.e., a decision related to investment risk. In the case of the Swedish Transport Administration, there is only one provider of cement.

When introducing a carbon tax on fossil-based emissions at a price-level in the range on what is seen on the market in Year 2022, namely of 80€/tCO₂, it is shown that the production cost of the cement reference case is largely increased and closes the gap between the reference and CCS case. Therefore, producing cement with CCS could become cost-competitive as the free emission allowances for the industry is phased out in the EU-ETS scheme provided the allowance prices continue to increase. From Russia's invasion in Ukraine there have been discussions on open part of the Market Stability Reserve to the market. This may result in a reduction of the allowance prices.

5. Conclusion

This paper builds on the concept of product chain analysis and has quantified the change in cost and CO₂-emissions when introducing CCS in the cement industry and sulfate pulp industry. The results show that the production cost of these basic materials increases by 230-260% and 75-131% when introducing CCS in the cement and pulp industry respectively. Moreover, by introducing a CO₂-tax of 168€/tCO₂ on fossil-based emissions in the cement industry, the production cost of cement with and without CCS would be equal. However, when considering the cost increase of the basic material in product chain perspective to end-product case studies, the production cost of the end-product (high-speed railway and disposable baby diaper) will only increase by 1.4-2.0% and 3.3-4.8% for the cement and pulp end-product case study, respectively. By applying CCS to the basic material production, the direct CO₂-emissions can be reduced by 90% and 77.5% for the cement and pulp industry, which results in a reduction of 30% and 32% on the respective end-products used as examples in this work.

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